

PROSPECTS FOR THE REALIZATION OF THE CONCEPT OF INFORMATION SOCIETY: OUTLINES FOR IMPROVING STATE POLICY

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Abstract. The article uses theoretical analysis to determine the prospects for implementing the concept of information society in the context of improving public policy. It is proved that the era of the information society, taking into account one of its key criteria, is coming to an end due to the reduction of employment in this sector. It is determined that in the current conditions of further development of the information society, the predominant employment should be dispersed relatively evenly between sectors or concentrated in some new sector. There are also qualitative changes with knowledge and information itself, which are the basis of the information society. Knowledge and information are beginning to transform into antipodes to some extent. There are certain dissonances. Many people feel a lack of awareness and difficulties in obtaining quality knowledge, despite the proliferation of information technology, and they have not become more informed or expanded their opportunities for obtaining it. Discussions are ongoing, ranging from whether the information society is being formed in accordance with the declared goals and to what extent these goals are being realized. On the other side of this spectrum, there is a discussion about the concept of the post-information society, as well as the unity of terminological approaches to the information and post-information society. It has been found that the vast majority of countries are involved in the formation of a model for adapting the information transformation of social development. Such changes at the global level lead to corresponding changes in the priorities of public policy in other countries to overcome the digital divide. It is shown that with such changes, technologically backward countries risk becoming victims of cybercolonialism by developed countries. This type of neo-colonialism may surpass the danger of raw material (traditional) colonialism that took place in the twentieth century.

Keywords: global institutions, public policy, public administration, employment, information society, information sphere, culture, post-information society, technology.

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Introduction

The concept of the information society was substantiated in the 1960s in the scientific works of Hayashi Y. Later, this scientific direction was joined by Bell D., Castells M., Nesbit D., Turen A., Webster F., and others. The information society was considered by the Japanese researcher Masuda Y. as a goal of public administration as an idea of national development in his scientific works that were implemented at the level of the Japanese government. Important in this context was the fact that the adoption of such a decision in some way contradicted the interests of the state bureaucracy. Thus, according to Masuda's project, the information society was supposed to be a classless and conflict-free society of consent, with a small state apparatus, which significantly reduced the importance of the state relative to previous stages of historical development [11].

A similar process took place in the United States, where Bell D. also developed the idea of post-industrialism [7]. At the same time, the term "information society" itself best reveals the new name of the post-industrial society, in which information is the basis of the social structure. This concept was further developed in the scientific publications of E. Toffler (the concept of three waves of civilization development: agrarian, industrial, post-industrial or information). The information society emerges when the majority of employment is transferred to the information sector, while the agrarian and industrial sectors retain a minority of the employed population. However, such a change in the employment structure implies not a quantitative, but a qualitative change in society, which causes a significant difference between the information society and the agrarian and industrial ones.

The purpose of the article is to determine, on the basis of theoretical analysis, the prospects for implementing the concept of information society in the context of improving the State policy.

Presentation of the main material

At the time the concept of the information society was being formulated, it actually already existed, particularly in the United States. In the 1950s, the share of office workers in the American labor market had already reached 50%. The vision of the information society began to take hold as a new form of society.

At the same time, interest in the concept of the information society was also growing in Western Europe. The information society was seen as an opportunity for the formation of a welfare state. This led to the proclamation of the information society as the most progressive form of organization of social activity, on the basis of which humanity is able to solve the previously accumulated problems of society [3; 4].

The socio-economic opportunities of the sphere of informatization are demonstrated in practice by the experience of the United States. Thanks to the information revolution, the United States has become a world leader in the same way as England did in its time as a result of the Industrial Revolution. In particular, in 1996, the US information and computer sector of the economy provided an increase in GDP by more than 6%. The information sector has become the main employer in the country. Also, along with the increase in jobs in the information sector, wages have increased. The information sector has also contributed to a significant increase in exports and has taken a dominant position in terms of investment in development and research (almost 40%).

Such indicators influenced representatives of political and economic elites in other countries. This phenomenon was perceived as a model of state-building and a benchmark for further development. One of the main factors of success of the USA is a long-term and consistent state policy of informatization based on political principles and focused on the implementation of strategic goals and objectives within the state program.

The countries of the European Union, having joined this process, formulate policies and activities in the information sphere on identical political principles. Informatization policy is implemented within the general system of EU technological development programs, of which

the European Informatization Program is an element. The purpose of these programs is to ensure accelerated technological development in key sectors. The European Union is making every effort to increase its competitiveness and reduce its technological gap, as well as to reduce its dependence on the United States, the Republic of Korea and Japan in the field of information technology.

The analysis allows us to conclude that the share of the information sector in developed countries determines the degree of efficiency of the economy as a whole. This sector of the economy is developing most dynamically in comparison with the creation of means of production and the production of consumer goods. The main trends are manifested in the steady growth of the information technology market and investments in informatization. There is also an increase in income from the provision of information and communication services and information technology products. This also applies to the main trend in the development of informatization due to the expansion of the Internet. In particular, while computer technology used to be the determining force in the development of the information market, today the dominance is determined by the development of intranets and the Internet.

The intensive development of information technology in the United States, Japan, and the EU has led to international technological competition and has also promoted cooperation in the field of global information development. The beginning of such cooperation is considered to be the adoption of the Charter of the Global Information Society (Okinawa, Japan) in 2000 [5]. This document declares that information technologies are one of the key factors of social development on a global scale, have a decisive impact on people's lifestyles, their work, and the interaction of citizens (civil society) with the state. The Charter also predicted that information technologies would stimulate socio-economic transformations, and that the development of the global information society would be based on the free exchange of information and knowledge and democratic values.

The Charter of the Information Society launched an intensive process of adopting new joint agreements, decisions, and conventions. An important trend was the involvement of new countries, which gave global importance to information development.

As a result of such processes, the vast majority of countries are involved in the formation of a model for adapting the information transformation of social development, which in the 1990s was translated into a practical plane of state-building by the leading countries of the world. Such changes at the global level lead to corresponding changes in the priorities of public policy in other countries to overcome the digital divide.

With such changes, technologically backward countries risk becoming victims of cybercolonialism by developed countries. This type of neo-colonialism may surpass the danger of raw material (traditional) colonialism that took place in the twentieth century.

In the process of global informatization, a situation is created when public administration at the national level begins to weaken and is subject to the influence of global institutions that are able to exert information influence on other countries and their governments via the Internet. National states become formalized, subordinated to global institutions, and humanity acquires holistic signs of unity.

This leads to a new phenomenon of systemic integration of humanity into a super-society. M. Castells, studying the trends in the development of the information society, predicted the transformation of the "material" culture of mankind into a technological paradigm based on information technology [8].

Ukraine has joined the global process of information society development. Information technologies have become widespread in Ukrainian society and have caused significant changes in lifestyles. There is a rapid transformation of network technologies into a fundamental cultural component, without which one cannot imagine a full life.

At the same time, the development of various cultural forms inherent in the information society is based on the already widely available IT infrastructure. The basis of this infrastructure is computer technology, which is complemented by the structure of other technological components of the communication process, including electronic, television, telephone and radio networks, satellite systems, which continue to be improved.

Along with the widespread use of information technologies in the cultural and everyday life of the world's population, there are societies in some regions that have not moved to information development according to socio-economic and cultural criteria. However, the spread of the global process of informatization is highly dynamic, and determining the degree of informatization for a particular society is an urgent task.

Futurists of the late twentieth century usually used one specific criterion (employment structure, etc.). The concept of "information society" is most often used in relation to modern cultural specificity, which implies informatization of all spheres of human life.

In 2008, as part of a number of measures to improve the management system in the field of informatization and development of the information society, Ukraine established the State Committee for Informatization of Ukraine, appointed the head of the National Informatization Program, and created the Interagency Council for the Development of the Information Society, etc. Ukraine introduced electronic document management in the system of government bodies, which was developed with the involvement of scientists, specialists from central executive authorities, business representatives, and the National Bank of Ukraine. This made it possible to integrate various information and analytical systems and ensure their effective interaction. On this basis, e-government was introduced. The responsible authority was the State Agency for E-Governance of Ukraine (established in 2014), which was also responsible for ensuring the implementation of the Government's policy of informatization and development of the information society, and the formation of digital information resources at the national level. In 2019, the status of this State Agency was changed and transformed into the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, whose purpose is to ensure the formation and implementation of state policy on: digitalization, digital development, digital economy, digital innovations and technologies, robotics and robotization, e-government and e-democracy, development of the information society; introduction of electronic document management; development of digital skills and digital rights of citizens; open data, public electronic

It should be noted that the development of national digital information resources is a guarantee of the state's information security and the provision of high-quality electronic and administrative services to citizens, as well as the guarantee of information sovereignty for Ukraine [10]. In Ukraine, there is an understanding at the state level that the information society is inevitable. No one and nothing can stop or delay it.

Therefore, an important task for the state is to implement effective measures for the regulated development of such a process. It is advisable for the state to campaign for informatization, to convincingly and clearly prove the practical importance of informatization for society. Otherwise, the country may find itself an outsider in global development. Ukraine has the prerequisites for this due to the high level of scientific personnel in the field of informatization, theoretical results, and technical solutions.

The overall positive prospects of the information society in developed countries contributed to its practical implementation in the early twenty-first century on a global scale. Today, the information society has become not only a scientific category, but has also gained popularity among businessmen, politicians, journalists, etc. This category is present in the legal and regulatory discourse. However, as a result of this popularization, the content of this category has diffused, and its use is marked by uncertainties and contradictions [2].

Recently, the literature has focused on the fact that information technologies have become so deeply integrated into public life and have caused significant worldview

transformations that it is already reasonable to talk about the formation of another stage of society's development - the post-information society. In 2016, the Ministry of Information Policy of Ukraine discussed the development of the information and post-information society. It was the first official event in Ukraine to discuss further prospects for the development of a new type of society [1].

With regard to the establishment of preconditions for the formation of a post-information format of social development, lobbyists from different countries from business structures in the field of new technologies are currently consolidating their efforts to promote their own interests on a global scale, in particular with regard to the concept of a post-information society. At the same time, the practical erasure of borders through the information space intensifies and facilitates this process.

In this regard, it is advisable to analyze the essence of the phenomenon of "post-information society", compare it with the "information society" and identify promising areas for improving public policy in the context of the development of the information society. It is usually noted that the concepts of information and post-industrial society describe the same reality - a society that is focused on information and knowledge as the main subject of consumption and production resource. Other scientific theories emphasize the dominance of the service sector rather than production in the post-industrial society. In this case, the information society is the highest stage of development of the post-industrial society.

Among the many scientific definitions of the "information society", it is advisable to distinguish the position of M. Castells, when the main criterion is the level of mediation of administrative, production processes, and everyday life by information technologies. In his opinion, the information society indicates a specific form of social construction in which the generation, transmission and processing of information based on appropriate technologies have become the main sources of power and productivity [8].

Another approach to this issue was presented by E. Toffler. In his opinion, the main criterion of the information society is the employment of the population in the information sector (over 50%) [12].

Subsequently, various researchers have expanded the set of quantitative and qualitative criteria of the information society, but the essence of this discussion has not changed significantly. In particular, sociologist F. Webster identified the following criteria: technological (emergence of electronic devices); economic (information technologies provide higher efficiency relative to other economic sectors); rebalancing of labor employment in the field of information technologies; development of the Internet and network technologies; formation of the information culture of the population [13].

The list of similar theoretical approaches to the criteria for defining the information society can be continued. However, in essence, these approaches are similar, differing only in the emphasis either on the information itself or on technical means. It is clear that information employment is impossible without sufficient development of technical means. In addition, for the predominance of employment in the information sector, proper automation of the industrial and mechanization of the agricultural sectors is also necessary. Agrarian societies appeared first, as a result of mechanization in which employment in agriculture is reduced in favor of the industrial sector. In turn, the industrial sector, as a result of automation and further computerization, requires fewer human resources, but increases the requirements for their quality. Therefore, the shift of employment in favor of the information sector also historically looks like a temporary phenomenon.

Many researchers have found a trend that in the conditions of the development of the information society, the dynamics of job reduction in the information sector is higher than the same trends in industry and agriculture. At the stage of the formation of the information society, J. Galbraith noted the futility of hopes for compensation by other industries for jobs that will be lost in industry. He argued that the result of improving the production process, as

a rule, is the replacement of labor by capital. In particular, this is due to the fact that equipment prices are more predictable compared to wages. Equipment costs have a higher level of stability compared to labor [9].

As a result, technical progress and the associated replacement of labor by capital contribute to increasing the stability of the activities of economic entities. The replacement of labor by capital also increases the safety of the technological structure. If pre-industrial societies were characterized by traditional methods of work, innovations appeared randomly, and labor productivity grew slowly, then for industrial society systematic innovations and increased labor productivity become a common trend. Thanks to technical progress, a smaller number of people armed with more advanced means and technologies are able to produce more goods and provide services, which reduces the need for human resources.

Thus, we can conclude that after a short period of increasing employment in the information sector, it is significantly reduced. Due to technical progress, significantly more jobs are eliminated than are created. The emergence of a highly efficient workplace causes the reduction of many less efficient old positions (professions). Most of the dismissed workers, who have outdated skills and knowledge, are not able to master new technologies quickly enough, and therefore cannot adapt to the post-industrial economy. In this regard, the established employment policy with an unemployment rate of up to 3%, which was characteristic of developed countries of the world at the end of the twentieth century, is under threat.

Conclusions

It is proven that the era of the information society, taking into account one of its key criteria, is coming to an end due to the reduction of employment in this sector. It is determined that in the current conditions of further development of the information society, the prevailing employment should be dispersed relatively evenly between sectors, or concentrated in some new sector. Qualitative changes are also taking place with knowledge and information itself, which form the basis of the information society. Knowledge and information are beginning to transform to some extent into antipodes. Certain dissonances have arisen. Many people feel a lack of awareness and difficulties in obtaining quality knowledge, despite the spread of information technologies, they have not become more informed and the possibilities of obtaining have not expanded. Discussions are ongoing, the range of which ranges from whether the information society is being formed in accordance with the declared goals and to what extent such goals are being realized. On the other side of this range, there is a discussion about the concept of a post-information society, as well as the unity of terminological approaches to the information and post-information society.

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